

The Collection of the Digital Twin Tools (20 October 2024)

Digital Twin Tool	Web-site
1 AnyLogic	www.anylogic.com
2 Tecnomatix	https://plm.sw.siemens.com/en-US/tecnomatix/
3 aPriori	https://www.apriori.com/
4 XMPro App Designer	https://xmpro.com/
5 Trendspek	https://trendspek.com/
6 Autodesk Tandem	https://intandem.autodesk.com/
7 Naera	http://neara.com/
8 Apian	http://www.apian.aero/
9 Virtonomy	https://virtonomy.io/
10 AISPECO	https://www.aispeco.com/
11 Azure Digital Twins	https://azure.microsoft.com/en-us/products/digital-twins
12 Unlearn.AI	https://www.unlearn.ai/
13 Ansys Twin Builder	https://www.ansys.com/
14 Bentley Systems	https://www.bentley.com/software/infrastructure-digital-twins/
15 Rockwell Automation	https://www.rockwellautomation.com/
16 General Electric	https://www.ge.com/
17 Mimic Simulation	https://mimicsimulation.com/simulation-software/
18 Veerum	https://www.veerum.com/
19 CADMATIC eShare	https://www.cadmatic.com/en/products/cadmatic-eshare/
20 Archilogic	https://www.archilogic.com/
21 Golem	https://golem.at/
22 Green Twin	https://greentwin.eu/
23 Value Chain Resilience GmbH	https://www.vcresilience.com/
24 Infinigrd	https://infinigrd.ai/
25 Nominal Systems	https://www.nominalsys.com/
26 Wearin	https://wearin.tech/
27 Agrilogic	https://www.agrilogicconsulting.com/en/
28 Livlet	https://www.livlet.com/
29 Twinzo	https://www.twinzo.eu/
30 Manufacture Oslo	https://www.manufacture-oslo.no/
31 Stanza	https://stanza.cc/lander
32 Kepstrum Inc.	https://www.kepstrum.com/
33 Ultrawis	https://www.ultrawis.com/
34 Circle Garage	https://circlegarage.com/
35 Thynkli	https://thynkli.com/
36 Neomorph Studio SRL	https://www.neomorph.io/

37 Urbim	https://urbim.io/
38 VERTLINER	https://vertliner.com/
39 Prevu3D	https://www.prevu3d.com/
40 TransformologyXR	https://transformologyxr.com/
41 WareBee	https://warebee.com/
42 Array Labs	https://www.arraylabs.io/
43 Eclipse Ditto	https://eclipse.dev/ditto/
44 Eclipse BaSyx	https://eclipse.dev/basyx/
45 iTwin.js	https://www.itwinjs.org/
46 SewerAI	https://www.sewerai.com/
47 Bosch IoT Suite	https://bosch-iot-suite.com/
48 DTCC Platform	https://dtcc.chalmers.se/digital-twin-platform/
Oracle IoT Production 49 Monitoring Cloud	<a href="https://docs.oracle.com/en/cloud/paas/iot-cloud/iotgs/oracle-
iot-digital-twin-implementation.html">https://docs.oracle.com/en/cloud/paas/iot-cloud/iotgs/oracle- iot-digital-twin-implementation.html
50 OpenSpace Group Ltd	https://open-space.io/
51 Trilleco DACH GmbH	https://www.trilleco.com/about
52 Thingstel	https://thingstel.com/index.html
53 vHive	https://www.vhive.ai/
54 dataArrows Inc.	https://www.dataarrows.com/
55 Process Genius Oy	https://processgenius.fi
56 WanderLens	https://www.wander-lens.com
57 DEO.care	https://deo.care
58 Metareal Inc.	https://www.metareal.com
59 LEAFES Corp	https://leafes.pro
60 Agritrack SA	https://agritrack.io
61 Candour.Digital	https://www.circulaid.io
62 Blackshark	https://blackshark.ai
63 Geogram	https://geogram.xyz
64 Karpine Technologies Pvt	https://www.karpine.io
65 EKORE Srl	https://www.ekore.it
66 F44	https://f44.pl
67 Cryptonize SL	https://www.cryptonize.world
68 AQUADAT	https://www.aquaradar.net
69 AgroConform	https://agroconform.com
70 VAIMÉE	https://vaimee.com
71 Neuno	https://neuno.io
72 Metis Labs	https://www.metislabs.tech/lander
73 triio	https://www.triio.io
74 Matterport Inc	https://matterport.com
75 Analytica	https://www.analytica.com
76 Phasmatic PC	https://www.phasmatic.com
77 EDY	https://www.edysolutions.eu
78 Silico	https://www.silicoai.com

